

Studies on coordination compounds of manganese-, cobalt-, nickel-, copper-, zinc- and cadmium(II) with urazine

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Complexes of urazine (H-Uz) with bivalent metals having composition $M(Uz)_2 \cdot nH_2O$ (where $M=Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn$ or Cd ; $n = 4, 3$ or 2) have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, physical and spectral data.

Complexes of 3,5-dimercapto-4-amino-1,2,4-triazole¹ and some other triazole derivatives² with various metals have been reported. We now report the complexes of 3,5-dioxo-4-amino-1,2,4-triazole (urazine) with bivalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Cd.

Results and Discussion

Urazine (H-Uz) in neutral or alkaline medium forms inner chelates with bivalent metal ions of composition, $M(Uz)_2 \cdot nH_2O$ (where $M = Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn$ or Cd ; $n = 4, 3$ or 2). The complexes with the ligand in its dianionic form expected to be formed by enolisation of both the amide groups could not be isolated. The isolated chelates are almost insoluble in water and common organic solvents, but they dissolve appreciably in DMF and DMSO. The DMF solutions of the complexes show negligible conductance values ($6-15 \Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) at 30° , supporting their non-electrolytic nature. The complexes are quite stable in air and do not lose water molecules over $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator at room temperature. The complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} on heating in air at $110-120^\circ$ retain two water molecules while the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes become anhydrous below 120° . The retention of two water molecules with the Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes indicates their coordination with metal ions, whereas water molecules lost below 120° are either held up in crystal lattices or weakly involved in hydrogen bonding with carbonyl oxygen or ring nitrogen atoms.

The room temperature magnetic moment values of the Mn^{II} (5.94), Co^{II} (4.87), Ni^{II} (3.35) and Cu^{II} (1.83 B.M.)

complexes fall within the usual range of six-coordinated spin-free octahedral complexes³. The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic. The electronic reflectance spectra display prominent ligand field transitions for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} but no distinct bands are observed for other complexes. The Mn^{II} complex does not display electronic spectral bands in the visible region due to very low intensity of expected spin-forbidden transitions. The reflectance bands of the Ni^{II} complex at 26930, 15530 and 9350 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ transitions in octahedral field^{4,5}. The computed⁶ values of ligand field parameters $10Dq = 9350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 962 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.92$ indicate moderately weak field nature of the ligand. The ligand field bands of the Co^{II} complex at 20410 and 8930 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ transitions in appreciably distorted octahedral field⁴. The prominent shoulder located at 19230 cm^{-1} and enhanced intensity of $d-d$ transitions support tetragonal distortion of the field. The calculated⁷ values of ligand field parameters $10Dq = 9982 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 713 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.72$ also suggest that the ligand urazine is moderately weak. The ligand field band occurring at 24100 cm^{-1} in the Cu^{II} complex is probably charge transfer band, while the broad medium band at 12800 cm^{-1} is attributed to $E_g \rightarrow T_{2g}$ transition or combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transitions in distorted octahedral field⁸. At LNT, epr signals of the Cu^{II} complex were found sharper and narrower but gave the same values for $g_{||}$ and g_{\perp} . The calculated epr tensors were found to be $g_{||} = 2.261$, $g_{\perp} = 2.066$, $g <av> = 2.13$ and $G = 3.95$. The value $g_{||} > g_{\perp}$ indicates tetragonal elongation and G value (~ 4) suggests absence of metal-metal interaction in the complex. Thus it is inferred that unpaired electron is present in x^2-y^2 orbital⁹.

A tetrahedral structure is suggested for the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}

complexes due to the absence of water molecules in the coordination sphere.

The ir spectrum of the ligand displayed NH_2 stretch at $3110\text{--}2860\text{ cm}^{-1}$ probably due to hydrogen bonding through amide oxygen. The ring NH stretch was observed as sharp and medium bands at 3332 and 3288 cm^{-1} . All the complexes displayed very strong broad and asymmetric band at $3400\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to a combination of $\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$, $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu(\text{NH})$ vibrations having appreciable hydrogen bonding. Besides, the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes showed two extra bands at 3340 and 3280 cm^{-1} attributed to ring NH stretch. The absence of distinct NH stretches in other complexes may be attributed to scrambling of ligand in octahedral field. The reduced intensity and occurrence of NH stretch band at the same wavenumber in the tetrahedral complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} indicates that at least one NH group is free and not affected on coordination. The free ligand displayed $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibrations¹⁰ at 1735 and 1660 cm^{-1} as strong and broad bands. The former band is feebly affected while the latter is appreciably affected from hydrogen bonding of the ligand. In six-coordinated complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} , the (CO) stretch is observed as broad and strong band at $1680\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ while it was observed at $1720\text{--}1710\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes. The existence of $\nu(\text{CO})$ band in complexes suggests that at least one (CO) oxygen is not involved in coordination. A slight blue-shift in $\nu(\text{CO})$ band can be attributed to weak to moderate hydrogen bonding with lattice water in these complexes. The δNH_2 vibration of free ligand observed as a broad band near 1624 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequency by $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes, indicating the involvement of NH_2 nitrogen in coordination. A new band in the complexes around $1580\text{--}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to formation of (C=N) group by enolisation and deprotonation of one of the amide groups in almost all the complexes. The $\delta(\text{NH})$ vibration of free ligand observed at 1470 cm^{-1} is not affected appreciably in its position but observed with reduced intensity on complexation. A number of ir bands observed in finger print region of free ligand at 1448 , 1246 , 966 , 815 , 788 , 755 , 672 and 605 cm^{-1} as medium to strong bands, are attributed to $\beta(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu(\text{N}\text{--}\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{C}\text{--}\text{N})$, NH out-of-plane, NH in-plane, NH_2 scissoring and rocking vibrations. These vibrations are not affected appreciably on coordination. A new band observed at $1070 \pm 20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes is attributed to $\nu(\text{C}\text{--}\text{O})$ vibration, which is absent in free ligand as urazine exclusively exists in ketoamide form in solid state¹¹. The strong and broad band observed around $630\text{--}670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in aquo complexes is indicative of rocking vibration of coordinated water molecules¹². In far-infrared region, the ligand displayed medium bands at 402 , 350 and 310 cm^{-1} due to ring deformation vibrations. The new bands located at $475 \pm$

25 and $428 \pm 12\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes are tentatively assigned to M–O and M–N stretching vibrations¹² respectively.

The ir spectral studies suggest that amino-nitrogen and one of the deprotonated enolic oxygen atoms of the ligand are bonded to the metal ions. The ligand thus behaves as bidentate.

Experimental

The ligand (HUz) was prepared by the reported method¹³. All other chemicals and metal salts used were of either AnalaR or E. Merck extra pure grade. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP-700 spectrophotometer and ir spectra on a Hilger-Watts H800 spectrophotometer at I.I.T., Delhi. Epr spectra were recorded at I.I.T., Bombay, using DPPH as g marker in polycrystalline form at RT and LNT. Magnetic measurement was made by Gouy method.

$M(\text{Uz})_2.n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} ; $n = 4, 3$ or 2): An aqueous solution of the metal acetate hydrate (0.005 mol in 40 ml water) was added to a hot aqueous solution of the ligand (0.01 mol in 30 ml water) with stirring. From the resulting solution (pH 8–9) the complex that separated out immediately, was digested on a steam-bath for 30 min , then filtered, washed with water and methanol and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 in a desiccator.

All the complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

References

1. J. P. Srivastava, B. K. Sinha, R. Singh and L. K. Mishra, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1797.
2. P. D. Singh, N. K. Jha and L. K. Mishra, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 282; K. K. Roy 'Anil' and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 795; P. D. Singh and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 21, 447; A. K. Sinha, P. D. Singh, B. N. Keshari and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 662; 1989, **66**, 408; P. D. Singh, A. K. Sinha, K. K. Roy 'Anil' and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 519; V. V. Ramana, K. Yamuna and K. Saraswathi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 666; S. N. Dubey and B. K. Vaid, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 774; B. Ramachandra and B. Narayana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 250.
3. L. Sacconi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 3400; F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry, A Comprehensive Text", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1969.
4. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968.
5. W. C. E. Higginson, S. C. Nyburg and J. S. Wood, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 463.
6. D. K. Rastogi, K. C. Sharma, S. K. Dua and M. P. Teotia, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 685.
7. A. B. P. Lever, *Chem. Educat.*, 1968, **45**, 711.
8. J. Ferguson and B. O. West, *J. Chem. Soc.(A)*, 1966, 1569; L. L.

- Funk and T. R. Ortolano, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 567.
9. B. J. Hathaway and D. E. Billing, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, 5, 143; A. Syamal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 64, 719.
- 10 J. Fujita, K. Nakamoto and M. Kobayashi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 3295.
- 11 A. K. Das, M. Nath and Z. Zulkerman, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, 21, 49.
- 12 K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 2nd. ed., Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1970; D. M. Adams, "Metal Ligand and Related Vibrations", St. Martin's Press, New York, 1968.
- 13 L. F. Audrieth and E. B. Mohr, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1953, 4, 29.